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Preliminary results of Antimilos geology and volcanic hazard assessment.

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Antimilos belongs to the Milos volcanic field, along with Kimolos, Polyegos and Ananes islets. All these islands are mainly or entirely constituted by volcanic products and are part of the South Aegean Active Volcanic Arc (SAAVA).

The Antimilos islet (Fig. 1), also called Erimomilos, with a maximum altitude of 686 m, is located at a distance of about 19 km from the port of Adamas at NW of the Milos island. It covers about 8 km², and it is uninhabited. The last human residents left the island in about 1960. The island is particularly steep and without roads and paths.

The geological information about Antimilos is limited (Fielder, 1841; Ehrenburg, 1889; Sonder, 1925, Marinos, 1960; Fytikas et al., 1986). The first and only detailed geological study of the island was published by Marinos (1960), and the only radiometric age available is 320 ± 50 ka (K-Ar method, rhyolitic lava) reported by Fytikas et al. (1986).

Due to these conditions and the limited geological knowledge concerning the area, the Hellenic Survey of Geology and Mineral Exploration (HSGME) organised a field expedition with an overnight stay at the island. The aim of that expedition and several others that will follow is to achieve a complete understanding of the geology of Antimilos, with the publication of a geological map, and an assessment of the possible volcanic hazard.

Nine different geological formations were identified and sampled on Antimilos. Additionally, several volcano-tectonic information and structures were recorded. The island consists of volcanic rock formations; no Alpine basement formations were found. The only post-Alpine sedimentary formation on the island is thin eluvial mantles in areas dominated by fragmented volcanic rocks. They consist of fine-grained materials resulting from aeolian and thermal erosion.

The main structures and formations are small volcanic domes and lava flows, mainly of andesitic and rhyolitic composition (Francalanci et al., 2005). The thin and long lava flows are usually andesites, while the thicker and shorter ones are more acidic, i.e. dacites or rhyolites. Domes and lavas are usually highly porphyritic, often characterized by large (up to ca. 0.5 cm) feldspars, and contain mafic enclaves.

Debris and ash flow fed by the collapse of lava fronts or steep dome slopes are also present. In a few cases, small units - horizons of mud flows were identified. The composition of their clasts is the same of the composition of the collapsed lavas from which they originate. Only in one case, on the steep slopes of the NE coast, an andesitic pyroclastic tephra layer outcrops, deposited by dense pyroclastic flows.

Based on the until now available information, pyroclastic deposits, which could be related to large destructive explosions, were not identified. The two main craters, located at the centre of the northern part (Fig. 1B) and at the southern part (Agriokastro; Fig. 1C), are not explosive. They ought to be created in the late phase of the volcanic activity, after the retreat and shrinkage of the magma due to cooling processes. Accordingly, the island was mainly formed by a mild effusive-extrusive activity.

Tectonic features are rare. Two major faults were identified, both on the NE steep slopes of the island. However, the arrangement of the volcanic centers strongly suggests tectonic discontinuities that functioned as magma supply routes and controlled the positions of the craters in a NNE-SSW direction. Some dykes are present, also having a NNE-SSW direction. Similarly, in Milos island, the main tectonic structures, which have been active from the Pleistocene until now, have a NNW-SSE direction.

Among the geological formations and structures identified on the island, no depositional or erosional horizons were observed that could suggest significant intervals of cessation of volcanic activity. So, it could be assumed that the volcanic activity was continuous.

Additionally, based on the until now available information, no hydrothermal manifestations, i.e. hot springs and fumaroles or hydrothermal alterations, are present. Also, no base or precious metal ore or industrial mineral occurrences were identified, in contrast to the Milos island.

Based on the fact that until now, they are not any new dating available, no solid suggestions concerning Antimilos' time interval of creation could be made. The only available dating (320 ± 50 ka; Fytikas et al., 1986) concerns the oldest rhyolitic lavas of the island outcropping along the northern coast (Fig. 1A). Comparing the volume and sequence of the

volcanic products with corresponding volcanic edifices of the southern Aegean, we could consider that the island was built during the last phase of volcanic activity of Milos, when the volcanic centres of Trachila and Phyrliplaka were created, i.e. around 360 ka and 110 ka, respectively (Fytikas et al., 1986; Zhou et al., 2020). Of course, this hypothesis remains to be verified after the dating of a sufficient number of selected volcanic samples, which have already been sampled.

Figure 1. Antimilos island. (A) The northern side of Antimilos island. (B) Main crater. (C) Volcanic domes in the southern part of the island and the center of Agriokasto lava dome.

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